

Modeling of the Near Field Coupling Between an External Loop and an Implantable Spiral Chip Antenna in Biosensor Systems

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Abstract—In this paper, the near field coupling between an external hand-held loop and an implantable miniature (1×1 mm) printed square spiral chip antenna used in bio-MEMS sensors for contact-less powering and RF telemetry is investigated. The loop and the spiral are inductively coupled and effectively form a transformer. The numerical results include the quasi-stationary magnetic field pattern of the implanted antenna, near zone wave impedance as a function of the radial distance and the values of the lumped elements in the equivalent circuit model for the transformer.

I. INTRODUCTION

In human space exploration programs there are several situations such as extravehicular activity, launch and de-orbit, and exercise in microgravity that require noninvasive monitoring of the physiological parameters [1]. The sensors used in monitoring these parameters have to be small, light weight, wearable and inductively powered. In addition, the data from these sensors have to be wirelessly transmitted and recorded. As an example, the progress to date in the development of an implantable biosensor system for monitoring pressure is presented in [2], [3]. In this paper, the near field coupling characteristics between the loop antenna in the external hand-held device and the square spiral antenna in the implanted sensor are presented. These characteristics include the quasi-stationary or the near zone magnetic fields of the implanted antenna and the wave impedance as a function of the outward radial distance. In addition, when the loop is placed in close proximity to the spiral, the two antennas are inductively coupled and effectively form a transformer. Therefore a lumped element equivalent circuit model for the transformer is also presented. Several researchers in the past [4–8] have demonstrated inductive powering and data communications in implantable biosensors. Tables I&II summarize the inductor geometries and their coupling characteristics, respectively. However, the unique aspects of our approach are as follows: first, in our scheme the spiral antenna and the pressure sensor are monolithically integrated on opposite sides of a single silicon wafer. Thus the antenna, the sensor, and the control electronics can be mass-produced using commercial CMOS foundry process. Second, the dimensions of our antenna (1x1mm) are significantly smaller which results in a very compact design for the sensor unit.

Table I: Inductors Used in Hand-Held Devices and Implanted Sensors

External Reader (Transmitter)			Implanted Sensor (Receiver)			Reference
Shape	Dia, (mm)	Self Ind, (μH)	Shape	Dia, (mm)	Self Ind, (μH)	
Single Turn Loop	50	0.15	Single Turn Loop	50	0.15	Huang & Oberle [4]
Circular Coil	90	26	Circular Coil	20	25	Hamici, et al [5]
Circular Coil	10	55	Circular Coil	4.7	65	Akin, et al [6]
Morphognostic Coil	48	3.0	Morphognostic Coil	48	3.0	Donaldson & Perkins [7]
Unknown	Unknown	14.2	Printed Square Spiral	4.5	21.6	Neagu, et al [8]

Table II: Measured Coupling Characteristics of the Inductors in Table I

Link Dist, (mm)	Coupling Coeff	Mutual Ind, (μH)	Rec'd Power, or Induced Voltage	Operating Frequency, (MHz)
90	Unknown	Unknown	2 mW	27
20 to 40	0.014 - 0.027	Unknown	80 V	2
5	0.082	4.9	20 V peak	1
15 to 35	0.009 to 0.07	Unknown	20 V	7.8
1	0.036	0.6	2.2 mW	3

II. NEAR FIELD CHARACTERISTICS OF IMPLANTABLE SQUARE SPIRAL CHIP ANTENNA

The inductive powering and telemetry principle in a biosensor system is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. For the purpose of analysis, the implantable spiral chip antenna is approximated by a single turn wire loop of radius a , with constant current distribution I_0 , and circumference less than one-tenth of a wavelength as in [9]. The wire radius is b . The magnetic and electric field components for a small circular loop in the near field region ($kr \ll 1$), where r is the radial outward distance, are expressed as [9]

$$H_r = A \cos \theta, \quad H_\theta = \frac{A}{2} \sin \theta \quad \text{and} \quad H_\phi = 0$$

$$E_\phi = -j\eta \frac{Akr}{2} \sin \theta \quad \text{and} \quad E_\theta = E_r = 0$$

Where $A = a^2 I_0 e^{-jkr} / 2r^3$, $k = 2\pi/\lambda$, λ is the free space wavelength and $\eta = 120\pi$.

The computed magnitude of H_r , H_θ and $H_{\text{sum}} = (H_r + H_\theta)$ as a function of the angle θ in the near field region is presented in Fig. 2. From this figure it is evident that in the near field region, the total magnetic field intensity is fairly uniform in all directions. Furthermore, the computed wave impedance Z_w , defined as $(-E_\phi)/H_\theta = j\eta kr$, as a function of the normalized radial outward distance r is shown in Fig. 3. This figure shows that in the near field region Z_w linearly increases from a few ohms to few hundred ohms as long as $kr < 1$. In addition, Z_w is independent of the loop radius a , and wire diameter b . In view of the above, the implanted antenna and the antenna in the hand held device are inductively coupled in the near field region and effectively form a transformer. $Z_w = 377\Omega$ when $kr = 1$ or $r/\lambda = 1/2\pi$ and Z_w remains constant at 377Ω for $kr > 1$ or in the far field region.

Figure 1.—Schematic Representation of the Inductively Coupled Powering and Telemetry Principle for Implantable Bio-MEMS Sensors.

III. LUMPED ELEMENT EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT MODEL FOR THE TRANSFORMER

The lumped element equivalent circuit model for the transformer is shown in Fig. 4. In this figure, the primary and secondary sides of the transformer represent the loop antenna

in the hand held device and the miniature spiral implantable antenna, respectively. The circuit elements L_p and L_s are the self-inductances and R_p and R_s are the loss resistances of the two antennas, respectively. The mutual inductance is denoted as M and is equal to $k_c \sqrt{L_p L_s}$, where k_c is the coupling coefficient. The capacitance C_p is part of the input impedance matching circuit. The capacitance C_s represents the parasitic capacitance of the spiral and the tuning capacitance such as, the capacitance of the pressure sensor. As an example, for the spiral and the loop reported in prior publications by the authors [2], [3], the computed circuit element values using expressions in [9]-[11] are presented in Fig.4. The mutual coupling M is determined as explained in [10].

Figure 2.—Computed Quasi-Stationary (Near Field) Magnetic Field Components H_r , H_θ and $H_{sum}=(H_r+H_\theta)$ as a Function of the Angle θ for a Small Loop Located in the x - y Plane. $a = 1$ mm, frequency = 403 MHz, $r = 10$ cm, and $I_0 = 1$ mA.

Figure 3.—Computed Near Field Wave Impedance of the Idealized Loop Antenna Versus Normalized Outward Radial Distance at 403 MHz.

Figure 4.—The Inductively Coupled Loop and Spiral are Modeled as an Equivalent Transformer Circuit, $L_s=117.6$ nH, $C_s=100$ fF, $R_s=56$ Ω , $R_p=3.45$ Ω , $L_p=0.43$ μ H, $M\approx 6.5$ nH when the two antennas are 5 cm apart.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The near field coupling between an external hand-held loop antenna and an implantable printed square spiral chip antenna for bio-MEMS sensors applications is analytically investigated. The computed results show that the total magnetic field in the vicinity of the implanted antenna is fairly uniform in all directions and the wave impedance increases linearly with distance. Hence in the near field region, the spiral and the loop are inductively coupled and effectively form a transformer for which a lumped element equivalent circuit model and element values are presented.

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